

Annex 9. Gender studies within the project W2B-PR-41-Turkey “Improving food security by enhancing wheat production and its resilience to climate change through maintaining the diversity of currently grown landraces”

Gender studies in wheat landrace restoration project in rainfed wheat cultivation areas in Iran, A case study of East Azerbaijan province

Fattaneh, Hajilu

Scientific Staff of Social Science Department, University of Tabriz, Tabriz, Iran

Introduction:

In recent decades, gathering of information on the living knowledge of people who have traditionally been involved in agriculture and animal husbandry has been important, and an important part of national government plans and transnational projects of international agencies have focused on these projects. Because this knowledge can be used to protect the available ecological resources to develop and increase food security in a rapidly growing world population.

Ethnographic studies in this field show that indigenous knowledge in each context is understood and maintained in different ways between different members of a single community. Thus, gender is also an effective variable in acquiring, retaining, and transferring indigenous knowledge.

Lack of sufficient information about traditional women's knowledge in agriculture, which results in a lack of knowledge of agricultural technicians and planners about the indigenous knowledge of areas, impedes the adoption of appropriate decision-making and policy-making strategies for the development of food security. Gathering and analyzing gender data is one of the important steps in this field to understand differences in the food production chain, controlling and managing the production and marketing of products.

Materials and methods:

This research is a qualitative study, using anthropological research methods in the field, and in-depth structured method of Interviewing with rural women individually and in groups. The research questions focus on the following main issues:

- 1 .Women's native Knowledge about seed and spike form, local names, quality of Product from landraces
- 2 .The role of women in the process of wheat production and processing of its products
- 3 .The impact and role of women in the decision to cultivate wheat varieties
- 4 .Women's motives for choosing and continuing the cultivation of wheat landraces
- 5 .The most important reasons for women to conserve and maintain wheat landraces

Research area:

The four villages in the East Azerbaijan province, from May to August 2019, were surveyed as described in Table 1. Interviews with rural women, either individually or as a group, were conducted by female agricultural researchers and experts without the presence of men as agricultural experts and rural men as husband, fathers or children of women answered the research question.

Table 1: Villages surveyed

City	Village Number	Number of Group / Individual Interviews	Number of Interviewees per Group	Total
Horand	2	2	12+ 10	22
Bostab Abad	3	4	3+11+12+10	36
Maragheh	2	2	14+13	27
Hashtrood	1	1	4	4
Total	8	9	89	

Results and Findings:

The research findings are based on the coding of categories related to women's indigenous knowledge about native wheat and the central category designation. The results of the initial categorization of the women interviewed without weighting the categories are summarized in Table 2:

The results of the categorization of the categories according to the knowledge of the women interviewed about the important issues of wheat production are summarized in Tables 3 and 4:

Table 2: initial categorization of the women interviewed

Women's characteristics	The field of women's awareness and knowledge
Women over 55, Often illiterate, Female-headed households	Detailed and exact information on seed forms, local names, appropriate season of cultivation, pre-sowing operations, reasons for selecting cultivar, seed required of each cultivar for specific area, taste and quality of crop, disease and pest recognition and how to deal with it, time and type of fertilizer required based on intergenerational knowledge transmitted, familiarity with wheat farming problems and issues
Women between the ages of 40 and 55, preliminary literate to read and write	General information about cultivating operations, awareness of differences in taste and product quality based on what has been learned, emphasis on production costs and economical cost over production quality, attention to training provided by government experts, awareness of differences in resistance

	and susceptibility to pests and diseases in different wheat varieties
Women under 40, Interested in immigrating and living in the city, women with secondary education and above	lack of interest in ecological knowledge, know some of the local wheat names as they heard, do not know seed forms, their characteristics and differences, not interested to acquire information about agronomic knowledge, provide some needed wheat products from local neighbors or markets.

Table 3: Women's knowledge of indigenous cultivars

Names of wheat landraces used by rural women	Women's knowledge
Agbugda	Suitable for wheat flour production for urban white bread
Garagilchikh	Suitable for producing quality bulgur
Girmizi bugda	High plant height and higher straw production, suitable for agriculture and animal husbandry, lower seed production efficiency
Girmizigin	Drought resistant but susceptible to lodging
Gizil bugda	Flour suitable for bread production that is resistant to mold

Table 4: Women's knowledge of indigenous cultivars

Problems and problems	women's knowledge
Reduction of active and young labors for agriculture	Interest in emigrating and living in the city, increase living costs and inadequate agricultural income
Extension training, agricultural mechanization, small farm lands	Experts emphasize cultivation of modern cultivars, comparison of the cost of cultivation of local and modern cultivars, the impossibility and economical use of mechanization in small farms
Decreasing women's participation in decision making	Reducing the role of women in crop production and byproduct processing

Lack of wages and financial facilities for women

Middle-aged and young women with insufficient ecological and economic knowledge do not consider agriculture to be part of their daily duties

Discussion and conclusion:

In recent decades, the rise of industrialization, the development of urban life, and the increasing opportunity to live and study in cities have led to a tendency to migrate from rural to urban areas, which has led to the migration of often rural youth and the decline of the farmer population. Promoting improved cultivars (relying on wheat self-sufficiency policy), changing economic conditions of the country, emphasizing on economic viability of improved cultivars regarding to production costs, mechanization of large-scale farming and commercialization of production are among the most important factors in the tendency of farmers to cultivation of improved cultivars and the losing the wheat landraces among farmers.

The prevalence of mechanized planting of new crops, which is also available to men, training courses for men, gradually caused eliminating women from the wheat production cycle and they also traditionally having fewer salaries, lower rights on farming, became far an far away from wheat cultivation and participation in selection of cultivable varieties. Unlike in the past, when women used to produce by-products such as bulgur, string and roasted wheat to sell and helping the rural household economy, women are now often responsible for the very limited processing of home products for livelihood use.

In most villages, bakeries with centralized baking of government-made bread have replaced traditional home-made bakeries, leading to the elimination and dramatic reduction of the need for flour at home and subsequently the elimination of rural mills. So whole wheat grains is sold instead of being converted into flour for domestic use. This has also reduced and eliminated the family's demand to maintain a minimal production of better-tasting wheat and nutrients from native varieties.

Although rural women in the past from the early stages had been involved in wheat production from cultivation to harvest and were producing various types of wheat based products, they had a great deal of knowledge and skills in wheat production and through They were also involved in the decision to cultivate different varieties. but nowadays, especially in areas with large agricultural areas, eliminated from the production cycle and deciding to produce field crops.

In all surveyed groups of women, rural women in each region least the known wheat landraces. They are aware of the difference between modern wheats and landraces in terms of production efficiency, resistance and susceptibility to pests and diseases, but today they have been left out of the wheat farming cycle for many reasons.

This has led to a gradual decline in indigenous knowledge of generations among rural women, which has led to a vicious cycle of increasing female knowledge and of course, social and economic factors exacerbate it also.

In mountainous and small areas that are not suitable for commercial or mechanized cultivation, most fields became small orchards or fields for legums and vegetables, where the responsibility for cultivation and labor is often left to women. The findings indicate that despite all the issues discussed, it is still possible to promote and return to cultivation of wheat landraces with the full support of the government in these lands, but women consider this to be in addition to their daily duties and demand for it and want special wages or financial benefits. Women are also want to receive specialized agricultural training on the use of mechanized facilities for wheat cultivation and these trainings appear to be one of the most important motivations for promoting cultivation of landraces in proper areas.

Acknowledgments:

The present article extracted from the results of the gender research project on the restoration of wheat landraces in dryland wheat cultivation areas in Iran. Hereby, the researcher sincerely thanks and appreciates all the women in the field research who patiently answered the questions and provided their information. It is also necessary to express gratitude and appreciation for the support and technical and financial support of international research center CIMMYT. I also thank Dryland Agricultural Research Institute, Dr Saber Golkari, DG of DARI and project leader, Mozaffar Roostaei and Ismail Zadhasan project coordinators. The researcher is an academic staff of department of social sciences is Tabriz university, thereby thanking university officials and coordinators who provided the researcher with the opportunity to participate in this project solely for ethical commitment.

Gender studies in wheat landrace project in Afghanistan

Sabera Ghaffari

CIMMYT-Afghanistan Staff

Summary

Women interviews

Talked to whom, where, how many:

231 women farmers were interviewed about their experiences on wheat farming in general and about wheat landraces in particular. We could connect with 126 women farmers in the province of Balkh, 100 in Kabul and 125 in Herat.

Their responses about

Landraces:

65% of respondents were aware about landraces and they were growing them, however 15% reported knowing but not growing because of lower yields. 7% of women farmers had mix of landraces and improved varieties on their farms.

Decision maker:

56% of women farmers reported that their husbands decided what would be grown on the farm; however, 29% of them said that they decided collectively.

Women role:

Sixty six % of women were involved in cooking or making bread but 27% of them also worked in field in operations like weeding. 48 % of them were involved in cleaning, weighing etc., whereas 42% were engaged in sieving and storing. 25 % of women farmers claimed that they were involved in all the operations of wheat production.

Landrace advantage:

34% of respondents claimed better bread taste, 30% of them found them to be more nutritious and 22% of women farmers liked landraces because of superior baking quality.

Figures representing the responses are below.

Full report is under preparation.

Women farmers' Involvement

Gender studies in wheat landrace project in Afghanistan

Elif Basak Aksoy, Emrah Koc

The biological knowledge of those who practice traditional livelihoods is in high demand by transnational programs to improve food security for the world's rapidly growing population whilst conserving invaluable ecological resources. Various agencies are openly accruing and curating what local, traditional, Indigenous, aboriginal, and rural people know about the biosphere. (Food and Agricultural Organization 2009; IAASTD 2009). The ethnosciences pioneered the study and curation of such biological knowledge in the modern era (Berkes 1999). It is becoming clear that such knowledge is maintained differently and irregularly between various members of a community, with various knowledges held more expertly by certain 'kinds' of people (Baumflek 2015; Müller, Boubacar, and Guimbo 2015; Voeks 1996; R. A. Voeks and Leony 2004). A prime example is ethnobiological knowledge associated with gender (Voeks and Leony 2004; Pfeiffer and Butz 2005; Camou-Guerrero et al. 2008; Müller et al. 2015). "The cultural construction of beliefs and behaviors considered appropriate for each sex" (Lavenda and Schultz 2015:375). Social scientists introduced the term gender as a way of talking about all those expectations and beliefs we load onto people with certain physical characteristics. Ecological anthropology focuses upon the complex relations between people and their environment. Human populations have ongoing contact with and impact upon the land, climate, plant, and animal species in their vicinities, and these elements of their environment have reciprocal impacts on humans (Salzman and Attwood 1996:169). Ecological anthropology investigates the ways that a population shapes its environment and the subsequent manners in which these relations form the population's social, economic, and political life (Salzman and Attwood 1996:169). In a general sense, ecological anthropology attempts to provide a materialist explanation of human society and culture as products of adaptation to given environmental conditions (Seymour-Smith 1986:62).

Main issues:

- Knowledge of women on wheat landraces
- Knowledge on wheat production
- Role of women in production process
- Role of women in decision process
- How can we motivate both men and women to participate in the project?
- What are the expectations from the project and from the project team?

Methodology

- We are using semi-structured interview method
- Our sample is consisted of women from the villages chosen for the project, both beneficiaries and other women involved in wheat production
- We are conducting both individual and focus group interviews
- Our male coworker conducts structured interviews with reeves and male farmers in order to understand their point of view on gender roles and also to check some information on wheat production we get from women as well as male knowledge on landraces

Summary of gender survey in Turkey

Using the semi-structured interview technique, informations were collected about landraces and wheat production, the role of the women and their effect on decisions in wheat production process has been investigated, how they can be motivated to participate in the project and their expectations from the project and project team has been questioned. In the project scope 10 provinces, 20 districts and 30 villages have been visited and interviewed with 164 women. It is aimed to protect the knowledge about wheat landraces by benefiting from the experiences of transferring knowledge from mother to daughter.

As a result women have information about wheat landraces especially who is older than 40 have detailed knowledge. Although mechanization and migration women have active role in agriculture. Farmers are planting different landraces for straw and home consumption. Plant height (straw) is important for livestock. Taste and convenience to bread is important. If they are planting in large areas the commercial value of wheat is important. They started to production of different crops instead of wheat because of less income.

For conducting same project activity in Iran and Afghanistan two colleagues, Dr. Fattaneh Hajilou from Iran Tabriz University and Ms. Sabera Ghafari from Ministry of Women in Afghanistan, has successfully completed the training course on Rural Gender Survey for Wheat Biodiversity Conservation conducted during 16-19 september 2018 in Aksaray and Nigde, Turkey. It is planned to continue surveys in project targeted regions and at least two provinces (two villages in each two district) will be visited.

Province	District	Village	Region	Women interviewed	Main results
Erzurum	Oltu	Inanmis	East Anatolia	6	Women have information about wheat landraces. The fields are smaller than 5 ha. and the production is for home consumption. Taste and compliance with secondary products is important.
		Basbaglar			
		Camlibel			
Malatya	Merkez	Beydagi	East Anatolia	16	Women have information about wheat landraces. But there is a direct correlation between age and knowledge. Fields are between 9-70 ha. Wheat has low commercial value and production is mainly for household consumption and straw for livestock. In course of time the wheat cultivated areas converted into apricot orchards. The role of women decreased with mechanization.
	Yesilyurt	Gorgu			
	Battalgazi	Karakoy			
	Hekimhan	Katil			
Manisa	Gordes	Gunesli	Aegean Region	20	Women older than 40 have detailed information about landraces. Wheat has commercial value. Fields are larger than 5 ha. Due to livestock the plant height (straw) is important. The role of women
	Akhisar	Hanpasa			
		Dogankaya			
	Selendi	Selmanhacilar			

	Kula	Gokceoren			decreased with mechanization. They started preferring the products that has more income.
Mardin	Midyat	Budaklı	South-East Anatolia	16	Women of all ages have information about landraces. They keep some of the harvested landraces seed for next year planting. Wheat is planted more than 10 ha for both home consumption and commercial value. Plant height (straw) is important for livestock. Their idea is landraces are more appropriate for climate. Although the mechanization the women is still active in agriculture. Taste, convenience to bread and commercial value are important.
	Savur	Icoren			
	Mazıdag	Omurlu			
Sırnak	Guclukonak	Fındık	South-East Anatolia	14	Women of all ages have information about landraces. They keep some of the harvested landraces seed for next year planting. Wheat is planted more than 10 ha for both home consumption and commercial value. Plant height (straw) is important for livestock. Their idea is landraces are more appropriate for climate. Although the mechanization women is still active in agriculture. Taste, convenience to bread and commercial value are important.
Tokat	Merkez	Ormanbeyli	Central- Black Sea	35	Women have information about landraces. Although the mechanization the women is still active in agriculture. Plant height is important for straw and livestock. Farmers are planting different landraces for straw and home consumption. Field size is between 1 to 40 ha. Commercial value is not important.
		Derekısla			
		Nebikoy			
		Tahtaoba			
Aksaray	Guzelyurt	Ihlara	Central Anatolia	9	Women have detailed information about wheat landraces. Although mechanization and migration women have active role in agriculture. They have high motivation on wheat landraces. Convenience to bread and plant height (straw) is important.
		Gokce			
Nigde	Ciftlik	Sultanpınar	Central Anatolia	18	Women have detailed information about wheat landraces. Although mechanization and migration women have active role in agriculture. They have high motivation on wheat landraces. Commercial value of wheat is important.
		Kitreli			
Karaman	Ermenek	Yalındal	Central Anatolia	10	Women have detailed information about wheat landraces. Although mechanization and migration women have active role in agriculture. Plant height (straw) is important due to livestock. Fields are between 5 to 80 ha. Commercial value of wheat is important. They started to production of different crops instead of wheat.
	Sariveliler	Cukurbag			
Konya	Bozkır	Dereiçi	Central Anatolia	20	Women have detailed information about wheat landraces. Although mechanization and migration women have active role in agriculture. Plant height (straw) is important due to livestock. Fields are between 5 to 80 ha. Commercial value of wheat is important. They started to production of different crops instead of wheat.
		Kovanlık			
	Hadim	Goynukısla			
		Selahattin			

The full report is under preparation.

Wheat Landraces and Gender Perspectives in Turkey: Consumer Expectations, Concerns and Willingness to Pay

Dr. Nurcan Atalan-Helicke, Skidmore College, USA

Executive Summary

The consultant (female, Ph.D.) carried out 6 focus groups with women in Turkey: One in Tokat (May 16, 2019), two in Balıkesir (May 23, 2019), one in Istanbul (June 29, 2019), two in Ankara (July 18 and July 19, 2019). A total of 40 participants were recruited through key informants. Only the participants in Balıkesir were paid in cash for their time because they traveled from suburbs of the town to the focus group location. The meetings were carried out in easily accessible public space in Balıkesir, Istanbul, and Tokat and at key informants' houses in Ankara.

In addition, a face-to-face survey with 25 consumers were carried out in Istanbul, who attended a public lecture organized by Artisan Bakers Collective (Kollektif Firin), a recently established initiative for home and artisan bakers, and a Q&A session with the consultant. 10 of these participants were female, 15 were male. This group of participants were more aware of wheat landraces and can name multiple wheat varieties beyond *siyez*. However, there was not a major difference with the focus group results in terms of household budget spent on food, places where consumers shop for food, where they get their information on clean and healthy food or how they consume wheat and wheat products.

All focus groups were carried out in Turkish, audio recorded and then transcribed. The QA session and the surveys were also in Turkish. The quotes in the report are translated by the consultant. No participant dropped out of the study.

Some of the characteristics of focus group participants are as follows:

- The youngest participant in the focus groups was 19 years old, the oldest was 74.
- Except three participants, all focus group participants were married.
- 32.5% of participants were in the age group of 36-45, and 30% were in the age group 46-55, making majority of the participants (62.5%) ages 36-55.
- All but one participant reported their income: 15 of them (38%) have a monthly income of 1500-2500 TL (250-417 USD). This income is in the income band of minimum wage set in Turkey: Minimum monthly wage in Turkey, as of 2019, is 2558 TL (total), and 2020 TL (net), equivalent of 427 USD (total), and 337 USD (net).
- 41% of participants spend 100-1500 TL of their household budget on food. This is followed by 28% of participants who spend 500-999 TL of their household budget on food.

Some of the findings are as follows. The quotation marks are used to highlight some of the codes used by researcher in the analysis.

- Participants shopped for food mainly from supermarkets, local markets (pazar, organik pazar, köy pazari) and, in Istanbul, from food cooperatives.
- Participants were generally aware of wheat landraces, and used different words to define them: “atalik” (ancestor), “original,” “siyez,” “Anatolian,” “memleketimin bugdayi” (wheat coming from my hometown).
- Participants consumed wheat products mainly as bread. About one third of participants said they have recently diversified their bread to sourdough, village, whole breads, but the price margins of these bread varieties and their taste expectations still facilitate them to choose the breads they are familiar with. Whereas several consumers in Balikesir expressed a strong preference for their “*koy ekmeği*” (round, cooked preferably in wood fired stone oven, about 1 kg), several consumers in Ankara preferred “*bazlama*” (thinner round bread like English muffin, about 300-400 grams each, cooked on stove top). In general, bread has emerged as part of “local identity,” “an indispensable item” of their diet.
- Majority of the participants stated that they receive their information about healthy eating and wheat from TV and the internet, followed by friends and neighbors.
- Participants stated that they prepare at least one home-made food item on their own: The variety of home-made wheat products include tarhana, eriste (noodles) and bread as well as other food items including jam, pickles and yoghurt.
- Whereas several participants have tried “siyez” at least once, they were also concerned about how expensive it is, how “it is produced everywhere” and “sold everywhere,” and how they cannot trust the products sold in the markets “without certification”
- Majority of participants were concerned about the health of their families due to the “extensive use of chemicals,” “hormones,” “genetically engineered organisms” in agricultural production. Whereas some participants expressed disappointment with the fact that “nothing grows without chemicals,” others were concerned about the expansion of markets that claim to sell “natural” food without regulation.
- Several participants expressed a general lack of trust to the agri-food system and its actors. Interestingly, at least one-fourth of participants were dubious of “organic” products, despite a knowledge of “the need for extensive monitoring” for organic certification. This lack of trust coincided with lack of trust to the state and its offices, producers, the markets, and the government.
- Whereas several participants complained about price premiums of organic food and free-range food, several others also expressed “willingness to pay more” for clean and good food.
- There are different markers used by participants for good and clean food, from seasonality to taste. Majority of participants also chose the food from their local markets (or originating in their environs) as healthy, good and clean food.

The full report of this activity is under preparation.